

SPACE-GROUP DETERMINATION OF THE CRYSTALS OF *p*-NITROPHENOL (METASTABLE), PHENACETIN AND TRIBENZYLAMINE.

BY MATA PRASAD, JAGDISH SHANKER AND PRABHAKAR N. BALJEKAR.

The paper describes the results of space-group determination of the crystals of *p*-nitrophenol (metastable), phenacetin and tribenzylamine. Dimensions of the unit cells of the three crystals have been accurately determined by taking X-ray rotation photographs. All the three crystals belong to the space-group C_{2v}^2 with Γm Bravais lattice. The molecules in the unit cell are asymmetric in each case.

In the study of these crystals $K\alpha$ -radiation from a copper anticathode was used. The lengths of the axes and the abnormal halvings were respectively determined by taking rotation photographs and oscillation photographs at an interval of 10 or 15 degrees about the three principal axes of the crystals.

p-Nitrophenol (metastable).

The crystals develop the following faces :

$$m(110), m'(\bar{1}\bar{1}0), q(011) \text{ and } q'(0\bar{1}\bar{1}).$$

They belong to the monoclinic prismatic class and the axial ratio found by crystallographic measurements is

$$a : b : c = 1.3836 : 1 : 0.3398 \text{ and } \beta = 106^\circ 55' \text{ (cf. Groth, "Chemische Krystallographie" Vol. IV, p. 106).}$$

The dimensions of the unit cell calculated from the rotation photographs (cf. Plate I) are :

$$a = 15.34 \text{ \AA}, \quad b = 11.15 \text{ \AA}, \quad c = 3.79 \text{ \AA}.$$

These give the axial ratio to be $a : b : c = 1.376 : 1 : 0.3399$ which is in good agreement with that obtained by crystallographic measurements.

Tables I and II give the list of reflecting planes with their relative intensities estimated by eye.

TABLE I.

Axial planes.	P r i s m p l a n e s				
	(hol).	(okl).	(hko).	(hko).	(hko).
001 m.s.	201 w.	011 v.s.	110 m.s.	250 v.w.	520 m.s.
002 m.s.	20 $\bar{1}$ m.s.	012 w.m.	120 v.s.	260 w.	530 m.
020 m.s.	20 $\bar{2}$ v.w.	021 m.s.	130 m.s.	320 v.w.	540 w.
040 m.s.	401 w.m.	051 m.s.	140 m.s.	340 w.	610 w.m.
200 m.	40 $\bar{1}$ w.m.		150 w.	410 m.	630 w.m.
400 s.	601 v.w.		160 w.	420 s.	640 w.m.
600 w.m.	80 $\bar{1}$ w.m.		210 s.	430 m.	710 w.m.
800 w.			220 v.s.	440 w.	720 w.
			230 m.	450 w.	730 w.
			240 w.m.	510 m.s.	810 w.
					820 w.

TABLE II.

General planes.

Plane.	Intensity.	Plane.	Intensity.	Plane.	Intensity.	Plane.	Intensity.
111	v.s.	22 $\bar{1}$	w.	411	w.m.	53 $\bar{1}$	w.
11 $\bar{1}$	v.s.	231	m.s.	4 $\bar{1}\bar{1}$	m.s.	54 $\bar{1}$	w.
121	w.m.	23 $\bar{1}$	m.	41 $\bar{2}$	v.w.	621	v.w.
12 $\bar{1}$	w.	241	w.	421	w.	63 $\bar{1}$	v.w.
13 $\bar{1}$	m.s.	251	w.	42 $\bar{1}$	w.	71 $\bar{1}$	w.
141	m.	25 $\bar{1}$	w.	42 $\bar{2}$	w.	72 $\bar{1}$	w.m.
14 $\bar{1}$	w.	31 $\bar{1}$	w.m.	431	w.	73 $\bar{1}$	w.m.
211	m.	32 $\bar{1}$	w.	43 $\bar{1}$	m.	81 $\bar{1}$	w.
21 $\bar{1}$	m.	32 $\bar{2}$	m.	51 $\bar{1}$	m.	82 $\bar{1}$	w.
21 $\bar{2}$	v.w.	331	m.	51 $\bar{2}$	v.w.		
221	m.	33 $\bar{1}$	m.s.	52 $\bar{1}$	m.s.		

If will be seen from the above that planes (h0l) are halved when h is odd and (010) is also halved. These halvings assign the crystal to the space-group C_{2h}^5 , which requires four asymmetric molecules. The number of molecules calculated from the dimensions of the unit cell and the specific gravity of the crystals, which was found to be 1.495, is also four (accurately 4.018). This shows that the molecules of the metastable form of *p*-nitrophenol in the unit cell are asymmetric.

Phenacetin.

The crystals develop the following faces :—

$a(100)$, $c(001)$, $m(110)$, $r(101)$, $s(102)$, $q(011)$, $t(021)$, etc.

They belong to the monoclinic prismatic class and the axial ratio determined by crystallographic measurements is

$a : b : c = 1.4213 : 1 : 0.8054$ and $\beta = 109^\circ 17'$ (*cf.* Groth, *ibid.*, p. 242).

The dimensions of the unit cell calculated from the rotation photographs (*cf.* Plate II) are :—

$$a = 13.78 \text{ \AA}, \quad b = 9.73 \text{ \AA}, \quad c = 7.82 \text{ \AA}.$$

These give the axial ratio $a : b : c = 1.416 : 1 : 0.804$ which is in good agreement with that mentioned above.

Tables III and IV give the reflecting planes observed in the crystal along with their approximate relative intensities.

TABLE III.

Axial planes.	P r i s m p l a n e s			
	(hol).	(okl).	(hko).	(hko).
100 s.	102 m.s.	012 v.s.	110 v.s.	330 m.s.
200 v.s.	202 v.s.	021 v.s.	120 w.	340 m.
300 m.	202 m.s.	022 m.s.	140 w.	410 m.s.
400 m s.	204 w.	023 m.	210 w.m.	420 s.
500 v.s.	$30\bar{2}$ m.s.	031 s.	220 s.	440 m.
600 s.	$50\bar{2}$ m.s.	032 w.	230 v.w.	510 m
040 m.	$60\bar{2}$ s.	033 m.	240 w.m.	520 w.
002 m s.		041 m.	310 s.	610 w.
		42 m.	320 v.w.	620 m.
				710 m.s.
				720 m.
				730 w m.

TABLE IV.

General planes.

Plane.	Intensity.	Plane.	Intensity.	Plane.	Intensity.	Plane.	Intensity.
111	v.s.	221	m.	321	m.s.	431	m.s.
111	v.s.	221	m.	322	v.w.	431	w.
112	w.	222	m.	322	m.s.	432	m.s.
113	w.m.	223	w.	323	m.	433	m.
121	m.	223	v.w.	324	v.w.	441	v.w.
122	m.s.	231	w.m.	331	m.s.	441	w.
122	m s.	231	m.s.	332	w.	442	w.
131	v.s.	232	w.	332	m.s.	511	v.w.
131	m s.	232	m.	341	w.m.	511	w.m.
132	m.	233	m.	341	m.	512	m.s.
132	w.	241	w.	351	m.	513	m.s.
141	m.	241	m.	411	v.s.	522	m.
141	w.m.	311	w.	412	w.	523	v.w.
142	v.w.	311	m.s.	412	m.	611	v.w.
211	m s.	312	v.w.	413	m.s.	612	w.m.
211	v.s.	313	w.m.	413	m.	621	m.
212	w.m.	313	m.s.	421	m.	622	w.
212	v.w.	314	m.s.	421	m.	632	w.
213	w.			422	m	711	m.s.
				423	m.	712	w.m.
				423	m.	713	w.m.

It will be seen that planes (h0l) are halved when l is odd and (010) is also halved. The crystal therefore belongs to the space-group C_{2h}^5 which requires four asymmetric molecules. The number of molecules calculated from the dimensions of the unit cell and the specific gravity of the crystal, found to be 1.202, is also four (accurately 4.00). This shows that the molecules of phenacetin in the unit cell are asymmetric.

Tribenzylamine.

The crystals of tribenzylamine have been found to develop the following faces:—

$$a(100), \quad c(001), \quad r(101), \quad r'(10\bar{1}).$$

They belong to the monoclinic prismatic class and the axial ratio found by crystallographic measurements is $a : b : c = 1.2242 : 1 : 1.0130$; and $\beta = 95^\circ 4'$, (*cf.* Groth, *ibid.*, Vol. V, p. 323).

The dimensions of the unit cell calculated from the rotation photographs (Plate III) are

$$a = 22.03 \text{ \AA}, \quad b = 8.92 \text{ \AA}, \quad c = 9.04 \text{ \AA}.$$

These gives the axial ratio $a : b : c = 2(1.234) : 1 : 1.014$.

This shows that the a -axis is doubled, that is, has twice the length expected from the ratio obtained by the crystallographers.

Tables V and VI give the list of the reflecting planes in the crystal, along with their approximate relative intensities.

TABLE V.

Axial planes.	Prism planes.									
	(hol).		(holl).		(okl).		(hko).		(hko).	
001 s.	201	m.s.	601	m.s.	011	w.m.	110	m.s.	520	m.
002 s.	201	w.	601	m.	012	s.	120	v.s.	530	v.w.
003 w.	202	s.	602	w.	013	v.w.	130	m.	540	v.w.
004 w.	203	m.	602	w.	021	s.	210	s.	610	m.s.
020 m.s.	203	m.	603	m.s.	022	w.	220	m.s.	620	m.
200 v.s.	401	s.	603	w.m.	023	v.w.	230	m.	630	v.w.
400 m.	401	s.	801	m.	024	w.	240	v.w.	710	m.s.
600 m.	403	w.	801	w.	031	w.	410	s.	720	w.
800 w.m.	404	w.	(10)01	w.m.	033	w.	510	m.s.	730	v.w.
(10)00 v.w.			(10)02	w.					810	m.
									830	v.w.
									(10)10	w.
									(11)10	v.w.

TABLE VI.

General planes.

Plane.	Intensity.	Plane.	Intensity.	Plane.	Intensity.
111	m s.	22 $\bar{3}$	m.	422	v.w.
11 $\bar{1}$	m.s.	231	m.s.	42 $\bar{2}$	w.
112	s.	23 $\bar{1}$	w.	423	m.s.
11 $\bar{2}$	m.s.	232	v.w.	42 $\bar{3}$	w.m.
114	w.	23 $\bar{2}$	w m.	431	m.
11 $\bar{4}$	w.m.	233	w.	43 $\bar{2}$	m.
121	w.	311	v.s.	433	w.
12 $\bar{1}$	w.m.	31 $\bar{1}$	v.s.	511	m.s.
122	w.	312	m.s.	51 $\bar{2}$	w.m.
12 $\bar{2}$	m.	31 $\bar{2}$	m s.	513	m.
123	w.	31 $\bar{3}$	m.	521	w.m.
12 $\bar{3}$	w.	321	m.s.	52 $\bar{1}$	w.
124	w.	32 $\bar{1}$	s.	522	m.
131	m.s.	322	m.s.	52 $\bar{2}$	m.
13 $\bar{1}$	w.	32 $\bar{2}$	w.m.	523	w.
132	v.w.	32 $\bar{3}$	w.	52 $\bar{3}$	w.m.
13 $\bar{3}$	w.	324	v.w.	524	v.w.
211	v.s.	332	v.w.	52 $\bar{4}$	v.w.
21 $\bar{1}$	v.s.	333	w.	53 $\bar{1}$	w.
212	m.	33 $\bar{3}$	m.	532	w.
21 $\bar{2}$	m.	34 $\bar{1}$	v.w.	53 $\bar{2}$	w.
213	w.	411	v.s.	53 $\bar{3}$	w.
21 $\bar{3}$	m.	41 $\bar{1}$	v.s.	542	w.m.
221	m.s.	412	w m	611	w
22 $\bar{1}$	m.s.	41 $\bar{2}$	m.s.	61 $\bar{1}$	m.
222	w.m.	41 $\bar{3}$	w	612	w.m.
22 $\bar{2}$	m.	421	m.s.	61 $\bar{2}$	w.
22 $\bar{3}$	w.m.	42 $\bar{1}$	s.	613	w,

Rotation photograph of p-Nitrophenol (metastable).

a-axis

b-axis

c-axis

Rotation photograph of phenacetin.

a-axis

b-axis

c-axis

Rotation photograph of tribenzylamine.

a-axis

b-axis

c-axis

TABLE VI (contd.).

Plane.	Intensity.	Plane.	Intensity	Plane,	Intensity.
$61\bar{3}$	w.m.	$71\bar{4}$	w.	822	w
621	v w	721	v.w.	831	w.
622	v.w.	$72\bar{1}$	v w.	$83\bar{1}$	w.m.
$62\bar{2}$	w.	722	v.w.	$83\bar{2}$	w m.
$62\bar{3}$	w.	$72\bar{2}$	w.m.	911	w.
$62\bar{4}$	w.	723	v.w.	$91\bar{1}$	w
632	w.	731	v.w.	$91\bar{2}$	w.
641	v w.	$73\bar{2}$	w.m	913	m.
$64\bar{1}$	v w.	811	m.	$91\bar{3}$	w.
711	w.	$81\bar{1}$	m.s.	921	v w.
$71\bar{1}$	w.	812	v.w.	$92\bar{1}$	v.w.
712	w.	$81\bar{2}$	v.w.	$92\bar{2}$	v.w.
$71\bar{2}$	w.m	$81\bar{3}$	v.w.	$93\bar{1}$	w
713	m.	$82\bar{1}$	v.w.	$(11)\bar{1}2$	v.w.

It will be seen that the planes (h0l) are halved when h is odd and (010) is also halved. The crystal, therefore, belongs to the space-group C_{2h}^5 which requires four asymmetric molecules. The number of molecules calculated from the dimensions of the unit cell and the specific gravity of the crystals which was found to be 1.074, is also four (accurately 3.99). This shows that the molecules of tribenzylamine in the unit cell are asymmetric.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
ROYAL INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BOMBAY.

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